

1 **ELECTRONIC SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS**

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3 Development and validation of a decision model for the evaluation of novel lung cancer treatments in
4 the Netherlands.

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28 A.1 Methods

29 *Fitting of a parametric multistate statistical model (parMSSM)*

30 The fitting of parametric multistate-statistical model (parMSSM) is carried out as a series of
31 nested competing risk models accounting for competing events (e.g., from L1T to L2T vs from L1T to
32 Death) and delayed entry (left truncation) for in-transit events (i.e., from L2T to L3 and from L3T to
33 Death)^{1,2}.

34 For each possible time to event (from event i to event j), a cause-specific hazard model is defined
35 as follows:

$$36 \quad h_{ij}(t) = h_{0j}(t)\exp(\beta_k^T X_{kl}) \quad \text{equation (A1)}$$

37 where $h_{0j}(t)$ is a time dependent baseline hazard of moving from event i to event j . $h_{ij}(t)$ is the
38 hazard function of moving from event i to event j at time t . β_k^T is the transposed vector of model
39 coefficients associated with covariate X_{kl} , with $l = 1, 2, \dots, n_{ij}$. n_{ij} – total number of patients at
40 risk at $t = 0$ for moving from event i to event j .

41 Equation (A1) can be fitted using a parametric or non-parametric framework, and fitting goes as
42 follow;

- 43 a) For fitting a specific event-time distribution, patients who experience a competing event are
44 censored at the time of the competing event.
- 45 b) For event time from in-transit events (from L2T to L3T, from L2T to Death, and from L3T to
46 Death), patients are not at risk for these movement until they have progressed to event L2T or
47 L3T, respectively.

48 For a parametric framework, a specification of the distribution function of the baseline hazard
49 $h_{0ij}(t)$ for all time to events is required³. In this study we restricted ourselves to three proportional
50 hazard (PH) distribution functions i.e., Exponential, Weibull, and Gompertz. Based on visual
51 inspection, gompertz distribution with monotonic hazard was the best distribution for time from L1T
52 to L2T and L1T to Death, exponential distribution gives the best fit for time from L2T to L3T and
53 L2T to Death. Because of the limited number of patients at risk for time from L3T to Death, an
54 exponential distribution was chosen. Covariates (baseline attributes) for each time-to-event model
55 were selected based on backward selection (cutoff p-value < 0.05).

56 *Construction of the microsimulation model: non-personalized strategy*

57 The microsimulation model was implemented as follow; Patients' profiles were sampled
58 according to the distributions, associations, and parameters described in the methods Sect.
59 "Parameterization of the non-personalized strategy". First, we sampled baseline characteristics
60 (attributes); gender, year of diagnosis, age at diagnosis, CCI, PS. Later, conditional on baseline
61 attributes, we sampled the treatment decision (BSC or treated). For treated patients, the type of
62 systemic chemotherapy (cisplatin containing doublets or carboplatin containing doublets) was
63 sampled taking into account the baseline attributes. Distributions and parameters used to sample
64 patients' baseline attributes and treatment decisions are given in Table A6.

65 Under the non-personalized strategy; for patients who progressed to second- and third-line
66 chemotherapy. In the second and third lines we assumed that patients have equal prognosis regardless
67 of the type of chemotherapy. Therefore, in the second and third lines, there is no specification of
68 chemotherapy regimens.

69 Lastly, patients' disease pathways were sampled conditional upon patients' attributes and
70 treatment decisions. Time to event was drawn from the fitted parametric distributions and background
71 mortality as described in Sect. "Parameterization of the non-personalized strategy". For competing
72 events, the event with the shortest event time was taken as the event that occurred for that patient. At
73 any disease event, patients could die due to other causes (DoC) described by background mortality.
74 The process was carried on until all patients were in absorption event (Death).

75

76 *Note: Sampling from truncated Gompertz decrH.*

77 Mathematically, a Gompertz distribution with monotonic decreasing hazard (call it, Gompertz
78 decrH) has a non-zero probability for a patient to have *infinite* event time (patient can live forever)⁴.
79 When Gompertz decrH is used in the presented model, the simulation was constrained such that all
80 simulated patients have *finite* event time (i.e., no patient lives forever). The constraint was
81 implemented by resampling the patient's event time until at least one of the possible competing times
82 for the event from "event i" has finite event time. Thus, to say, sampling from "*truncated Gompertz*
83 *decrH*" distribution.

84 The consequence of truncation is that simulated data from truncated Gompertz have higher
85 hazard (shorter time to events, i.e., event time distribution is shifted to the left) compared to the actual
86 hazard used to simulate the data. Thus, the hazard rate re-estimated from simulated data (outHR) is
87 higher than the hazard rate used to obtain the simulated data (inHR). The magnitude of the difference
88 between outHR and inHR depends on the strength of inHR. The lower inHR, the higher the number of
89 patients with "infinite time" to be resampled, the higher the difference between outHR and inHR.

90 For the non-personalized strategy (patients treated with first-line chemotherapies), only 0.8%
91 of patients had their event time from L1T to L2T and Death resampled after first having “infinite
92 times” in both time to events (i.e., from L1T to L2T and from L1T to Death). However, for a
93 personalized strategy (patients treated with first-line targeted therapies or immunotherapy), about 12
94 percent of patients had their event time from L1T to L2T and Death resampled after first having
95 “infinite times” in both times to events (i.e., from L1T to L2T and L1T to Death).

96 To simulate treatment effect from a randomized clinical trials (RCT) for targeted therapy or
97 immunotherapy compared to chemotherapy in the personalized strategy, a progression-free hazard for
98 L1T to L2T and from L1T to Death (inHR) had to be calibrated. Calibration was done such that
99 simulated results for outHR equal the progression-free hazard rate from the RCT (rctHR). The outHR
100 was re-estimated by a coxPH model with cut-off time of 20 months from the start of first-line
101 treatment to mimic a limited follow-up in RCT. For example, for the EGFR subgroup treated with
102 first-line gefitinib, inHR of 0.38 was used to have an outHR of 0.43 which matches to the rctHR in a
103 network meta-analysis ⁵. Table A4 provides the rctHR and inHR for each molecular subgroup
104 simulated in the personalized strategy. For the Immunotherapy treated subgroup, inHR was given
105 under 23 percent long-term survivor fraction and 0 percent long-term survivor fraction as described in
106 Sect. “Adjustment of the non-personalized strategy to simulate a personalized treatment strategy” of
107 the main text.

108 **A.2 Tables**

109 Table A1. Distribution of baseline characteristics for patients with advanced (inoperable) non-
 110 squamous NSCLC diagnosed between 2008 and 2014

Variable	Non-squamous Cell		
	Systemic	BSC	All
Year (%)			
2008	82 (10.7)	211 (14.7)	293 (13.3)
2009	91 (12.0)	205 (14.3)	296 (13.5)
2010	95 (12.5)	208 (14.5)	303 (13.8)
2011	109 (14.3)	2015 (15.0)	324 (14.8)
2012	137 (18.0)	195 (13.6)	332 (15.1)
2013	126 (16.6)	192 (13.4)	318 (14.5)
2014	121 (16.0)	209 (14.6)	330 (15.0)
Gender (%)			
Male	432 (56.8)	849 (59.2)	1281 (58.3)
Female	329(43.2)	587 (40.8)	915 (41.7)
Age			
Mean ± std. Error	62.5 ± 0.350	68.9 ± 0.289	66.7 ± 0.234
PS (%)			
Good (0 – 1)	640 (84.1)	731 (50.9)	1371 (62.4)
Bad (2 – 4)	86 (11.3)	598 (41.7)	684 (31.1)
Unknown	35 (4.6)	106 (7.4)	141 (6.4)
CCI (%)			
Good (1 – 2)	718(94.3)	1266 (88.2)	1984 (90.3)
Bad (> 2)	43(5.7)	169 (11.8)	212 (9.7)
Histology (%)			
Adenocarcinoma	564 (74.1)	956 (66.6)	1520 (69.2)
Large cell	89 (11.7)	223 (15.5)	312 (14.2)
Other or NOS	108 (14.2)	256 (17.8)	364 (16.6)
First Line Treatment (%)			
Cisp. D			
Cisplatin-pemetrexed	291 (38.2)	-	291 (13.3)
Cisplatin-gemcitabine	90 (11.8)	-	90 (4.1)
Carbo. D			
Carboplatin-pemetrexed	195 (25.6)	-	195 (8.9)
Carboplatin-gemcitabine	87 (11.4)	-	87 (4.0)
Bevacizumab- carboplatin- paclitaxel	60 (7.9)	-	60 (2.7)
Carboplatin-docetaxel	38 (5.0)	-	38 (1.7)
BSC	-	-	65.34
Total	761 (34.7)	1435 (65.3)	2196 (100)

111 PS, Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group performance status; CCI, Charlson comorbidity
 112 index; Year, year of diagnosis; Age, age at diagnosis; BSC, best supportive care; Systemic, first-
 113 line systemic chemotherapy; Cisp. D, cisplatin doublet chemotherapy; Carbo. D, carboplatin
 114 doublet chemotherapy; std. Error – standard error of the mean.

115 NB. This table provides description of 2196 non-squamous NSCLC patients received first-line
 116 standard chemotherapy or best supportive care, for more details on the complete cohort, we
 117 refer to Cramer-van der Welle et al., 2018 ⁶.

118 Table A2. Bivariate association of baseline characteristics and first-line treatment decision for patients
 119 with advanced (inoperable) non-squamous NSCLC diagnosed between 2008 and 2014

Variables		Methods	Test-statistic and pvalues			% sim. pv <0.05
Variable 1	Variable 2		Statistic	df	pvalue	
Year	Gender	χ^2	1.94	6	0.925	6
	PS	χ^2	91.87	12	<0.0001	100
	CCI	χ^2	5.291	6	0.507	5
	Treat (Syst or BSC)	χ^2	19.82	6	0.003	97
	Syst (Cisp. D or Carb. D)	χ^2	8.01	6	0.237	7
	Age	Anova	1.971	6; 2189	0.064	6
Gender	PS	χ^2	2.97	2	0.227	25
	CCI	χ^2	14.34	1	0.0002	98
	Treat (Syst or BSC)	χ^2	1.078	1	0.299	44
	Syst (Cisp. D or Carb. D)	χ^2	4.07	1	0.044	8
	Age	ttest	6.10	1865.7	<0.0001	100
PS	CCI	χ^2	24.89	2	<0.0001	100
	Treat (Syst or BSC)	χ^2	240.87	2	<0.0001	100
	Syst (Cisp. D or Carb. D)	χ^2	10.61	2	0.005	93
	Age at Diagnosis	Anova	46.18	2; 2193	<0.0001	100
CCI	Treat (Syst or BSC)	χ^2	20.70	1	<0.0001	100
	Syst (Cisp. D or Carb. D)	χ^2	1.60	1	0.2059	100
	Age	ttest	-8.86	273.9	<0.0001	100
Treat (Syst or BSC)	Age	ttest	14.14	1727.7	<0.0001	100
Type of Syst (Cisp. D or Carb. D)	Age	ttest	-4.96	758.8	<0.0001	100

120 χ^2 , Chi-square test of association; Anova, one way analysis of variance; ttest, two independent
 121 samples student's T test; PS, Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group performance status; CCI, Charlson
 122 comorbidity index; Year, year of diagnosis; Age, age at diagnosis; BSC, best supportive care; Syst,
 123 first-line systemic chemotherapy; Cisp. D, Cisplatin doublet chemotherapy; Carbo. D, Carboplatin
 124 doublet chemotherapy; % sim. pv \leq 0.05, percentage of simulations with p-value less than 0.05 out of
 125 1000 runs. Each run had 2196 simulated patients.

126 Table A3. Prevalence of molecular biomarkers in the population

Biomarker (subgroup)	Proportion	Standard error	Reference
EGFR _(classic) ^a	0.07	0.008	7
EGFR _(non-classic) ^b	0.01	0.001	7
ALK	0.02	0.002	7
ROS1	0.019	0.002	8
BRAF _(V600E)	0.021	0.002	9
NTRK _(1,2,3)	0.0017	-	10
MET _(amp / exon 14 sk)	0.014	0.001	9
RET	0.017	0.002	9
KRAS	0.28	0.029	7
No / Unknown	0.5473 ^c	-	-
For those tested for PD-L1			
PD-L1 ≥ 50%	0.25 ^d		11
PD-L1 < 50%	0.75 ^e	-	11

127 ^a Classic activating EGFR mutations (exon 19 deletions and exon 21 L858R point mutations).

128 ^b Non-classic activating EGFR mutations, resistance mutations, and other mutations.

129 ^c 1 minus sums all molecular markers.

130 ^d out of patients with unknown or without molecular biomarkers or had KRAS / MET / RET
 131 mutations.

132 ^e 1 minus PD-L1 ≥ 50%.

133 Table A4. First-line treatment and PFS HR per molecular subgroup

Biomarker	IL Treat	Control	PFS HR (95% CI)	Reference	inHR	
EGFR _(classic) ^a	Gefitinib	PDCT	0.43 (0.37 – 0.49)	5	0.3817	
EGFR _(classic) ^a	Erlotinib	PDCT	0.36 (0.30 – 0.43)	5	0.2518	
EGFR _(classic)	Prognostic value	-	0.82 (0.66 – 1.03)	12 (dig) ^c	0.8009	
EGFR _(non-classic) ^b	Afatinib	PDCT	0.40 (0.20 – 0.83)	12c	0.2586	
ALK	Alectinib	Crizotinib	0.47 (0.34 – 0.65)	13	-	
ALK	Crizotinib	PDCT	0.45 (0.35 – 0.60)	14	0.3339	
ALK	Alectinib	PDCT	0.212 ^d	Assumption	0.0032 ^d	
ALK	Prognostic value	-	0.80 (0.70 – 0.90)	15	0.7731	
ROS1	Crizotinib	-	0.45 (0.35 – 0.60)	14,16 e	0.3339	
BRAF _(V600E)	Dabrafenib & Trametinib	-	0.67 (0.53 – 0.84)	17,18 f	0.6247	
NTRK _(1,2,3)	Larotrectinib	-	0.82 (0.66 – 1.03)	12,19 g	0.8009	
MET _(amp / exon 14 sk)	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-	
RET	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-	
HER2	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-	
KRAS	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-	
No / Unknown	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-	
<i>Long-term survivor fraction</i>					23%	0%
PD-L1 ≥50%	Pembrolizumab	PDCT	0.50 (0.37 – 0.68)	20	0.7546	0.4070
PD-L1 ≥50%	Pembro & PDCT	PDCT	0.36 (0.25 – 0.52)	21	0.4376	0.1995
PD-L1 1-49%	Pembro & PDCT	PDCT	0.55 (0.34 – 0.90)	21	0.8715	0.4726

134 IL Treat, first-line treatment; Control, control arm treatment in randomized control trial (RCT); PFS HR, progression free

135 hazard rate; CI, confidence interval; inHR, calibrated hazard rate used in Truncated Gompertz distribution to simulate cohort

136 with novel treatment effect as the one observed in RCT (i.e., PFS HR).

137 ^a Classic activating EGFR mutations (exon 19 deletions and exon 21 L858R point mutations).

138 ^b Non-classic activating EGFR mutations, resistance mutations, and other mutations.

139 ^c Special request to the author to provide PFS HR, the method used can be obtained from the original work of Simons et al. ¹².

140 ^d Assumed that the hazard ratio (HR) of alectinib compared to chemotherapy (PDCT) is equal to the product of HR of alectinib compared to

141 crizotinib and HR of crizotonib compared to PDCT for patient with an ALK mutations i.e., $0.47 * 0.45 = 0.212$.

142 ^e No literature evidence for PFS HR, it was assumed that treatment effect will be the same as crizotinib in ALK patients.

143 ^f No literature evidence for PFS HR, it was assumed that treatment effect will be the same as dabrafenib and trametinib in
144 melanoma BRAF_{val1600} patients compared to dabrafenib and placebo.

145 ^g There is no evidence in the literature for PFS HR, we assumed that the effect of treatment will be the same as the prognostic value of EGFR_{classic}.

146 Table A5. Second-line treatment recommendation and PPFS HR per molecular subgroup and per first-line treatment

Biomarker	1L Treat	2L Treat	PPFS HR	Treat arm vs Control arm	References
EGFR <small>(classic)</small>	Gefitinib	Cis + Pem	N/A	-	-
EGFR <small>(classic)</small>	Erlotinib	Cis + Pem	N/A	-	-
EGFR <small>(non-classic)</small>	Afatinib	Cis + Pem	N/A	-	-
ALK	Alectinib	Lorlatinib	0.49 (0.37 – 0.64)	Crizotinib vs CT ^a	22
ROS1	Crizotinib	Cis + Pem	N/A	-	-
BRAF <small>(V600E)</small>	Dabraf & Tramet	PDL1 ≥ 50: Pemb	0.59 (0.44 – 0.78)	Pembro (2 gm/kg) vs CT	23
BRAF <small>(V600E)</small>	Dabraf & Tramet	PDL1 < 50: Pemb + Chem	0.59 (0.44 – 0.78)	Pembro (2 gm/kg) vs CT ^b	23
NTRK <small>(1,2,3)</small>	Larotrectinib	Cis + Pem	N/A	-	-
MET <small>(amp / exon 14 sk)</small>	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-
RET	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-
HER2	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-
KRAS	depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-
No / Unknown	Depends PD-L1	-	-	-	-
PD-L1 ≥50%	Pembrolizumab	Cis + Pem	N/A	-	-
PD-L1 ≥50%	Pembro & PDCT	Docetaxel	N/A	-	-
PD-L1 1-49%	Pembro & PDCT	Docetaxel	N/A	-	-

147 1L Treat, first-line treatment; 2L Treat, second-line treatment; PPFS HR, post-progression free survival hazard ratio (i.e., Hazard
 148 ratio for 2L); CT, single dose chemotherapy (pemetrexed or docetaxel); Cis, Cisplatin, Pem, pemetrexed; Pembro, pembrolizumab;
 149 PDCT, platinum-based doublets; N/A, No adjustment on hazard rate.

150 We have assumed that, the treatment effect in second-line is independent of first-line treatment.

151 ^a Lorlatinib assumed to have similar effectiveness as second line crizotinib in ALK mutated patients.

152 ^b Assumed the effect of second line pembrolizumab monotherapy.

153 Table A6. Regression model describing the association between baseline characteristics and
 154 first-line treatment for patients with advance (inoperable) non-squamous NSCLC diagnosed
 155 between 2008 and 2014

Res. Var	Model type	Distribution	Scale	Covariate	Coefficient	95% CI
Age	Linear	normal	Linear	Intercept	67.88	67.28; 68.47
				Gender: F	-2.90	-3.83; -1.98
				Sigma	10.85	
CCI CCI (bad)	Logistic	Binomial	Logit	Intercept	-5.88	-6.98; -4.83
				Age	0.06	0.04; 0.07
				Gender: F	-0.49	-0.81; -0.18
PS PS (obs)	Logistic	Binomial	Logit	Intercept	1.84	1.52; 2.19
				Yr2009	1.16	0.55; 1.82
				Yr2010	0.19	-0.29; 0.68
				Yr2011	1.11	0.53; 1.74
				Yr2012	0.46	-0.03; 0.97
				Yr2013	2.52	1.59; 3.73
				Yr2014	3.26	2.06; 5.08
PS (bad) ^a	Logistic	Binomial	Logit	Intercept	-3.32	-3.99; -2.66
				Yr2009	-0.01	-0.37; 0.36
				Yr2010	0.16	-0.21; 0.52
				Yr2011	-0.04	-0.39; 0.32
				Yr2012	-0.49	-0.86; -0.12
				Yr2013	-0.21	-0.57; 0.15
				Yr2014	-0.27	-0.63; 0.08
				Age	0.04	0.03; 0.05
				CCI: bad	0.52	0.22; 0.83
Treat Treat (sys)	Logistic	Binomial	Logit	Intercept	2.78	2.12; 3.44
				Yr2009	0.03	-0.36; 0.42
				Yr2010	0.27	-0.12; 0.65
				Yr2011	0.29	-0.08; 0.67
				Yr2012	0.57	0.21; 0.94
				Yr2013	0.48	0.11; 0.85
				Yr2014	0.41	0.04; 0.78
				Age	-0.05	-0.06; -0.04
				PS: bad	-1.64	-1.90; -1.39
				PS: miss	-0.81	-1.24; -0.40
CCI: bad	-0.39	-0.77; -0.01				
Type of Sys ^b Sys (Carbo)	Logistic	Binomial	Logit	Intercept	-2.51	-3.52; -1.53
				PS: bad	0.58	0.11; 1.06
				PS: miss	-0.87	-1.65; -0.15
				Age	0.04	0.02; 0.06

156 Res. Var, response variable; Model type, regression model type; Distribution, type of statistical
 157 distribution assumed for Res. Var; Scale, scale of linear predictor used to model Res. Var via
 158 Model type (e.g., if Res. Var assumed to have a normal distribution, then linear scale is used to
 159 model via linear regression); 95% CI, 95% confidence interval of regression coefficients (lower;
 160 upper); Age, age at diagnosis; F, Female; sigma, standard error of linear regression; CCI,

161 Charlson comorbidity Index, grouped as good or bad; PS, Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group
162 Performance Status (obs, PS was observed and grouped as bad or good); Yr, year of diagnosis;
163 Treat, decision to treat with systemic chemotherapy (Sys) or best supportive care (BSC); Type
164 of Sys, Type of systemic chemotherapy administered, grouped as Carboplatin doublets (Carbo.
165 D) and Cisplatin doublets (Cisp.D).
166 ^a fitted on a subset of patients with observed PS.
167 ^b fitted on a subset of patients received systemic chemotherapy.

168 Table A7. Time-to-event estimates of disease model (Fig. 1)

Term	Trans01 ^a	Trans04 ^a	Trans12 ^b	Trans14 ^b	Trans23 ^b	Trans24 ^b	Trans34 ^b
Distribution	<i>Log-logistic</i>	<i>Log-normal</i>	<i>Gompertz</i>	<i>Gompertz</i>	<i>Exponential</i>	<i>Exponential</i>	<i>Exponential</i>
Shape	0.9970*	-0.2110*	-0.2993 ⁺	-0.3369 ⁺	-	-	-
Intercept	-2.5490*	-1.3330*	0.5231 ⁺	0.1003 ⁺	-1.3590	-0.252	-0.363
Treat1g: Carb. D	-	-	0.1969	0.1457	0.4420	0.501*	0.005
PS:	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bad	-	0.8150*	-	0.4295*	-	-	-
Unkn	-	0.8250*	-	0.2050	-	-	-
Gender: Female	-0.107*	-0.1340*	-0.3281*	-	-0.814*	-0.510*	-
Age	-	-	-0.0233*	-	-0.044*	-	-

169 Treat1g, first-line systemic treatment groups; Carb. D, Carboplatin doublets compared to Cisplatin doublets; PS, ECOG
 170 performance status (Bad, ie., PS 2 or higher, Unkn, ie., unknown PS compared to good, ie., PS 0 or 1); Age, age at
 171 diagnosis in years.

172 Events: 0 is DIAG, diagnosis of advanced (inoperable) NSCLC; 1 is L1T, start of first-line treatment; 2 is L2T, start of
 173 second-line treatment; 3 is L3T, the start of third-line treatment; and 4 is death.

174 Time-to-events: Trans01, from DIAG to L1T; Trans04, from DIAG to death; Trans12, from L1T to L2T; Trans14, from
 175 L1T to death; Trans23, from L2T to L3T; Trans24, from L2T to death; Trans34, from L3T to death. (see Fig. 1, of the main
 176 text).

177 * Significant at alpha level of 0.05.

178 ⁺ p-value / CI not reported.

179 ^a Fitted as sub-distribution model.

180 ^b fitted as parametric multistate statistical model (parMSSM).

181 Table A8. Comparison of real-world, RCT, and modelled survival estimates

	Real-world			RCT	Modelled	
	Netherlands Cramer-van der Welle et al., ²⁴	US Velcheti et al., ^{25 a} Waterhouse et al., ^{26 b}			Cure rate: 0%	Cure rate: 23%
PD-L1 ≥ 50%; Pembrolizumab monotherapy				5 year update Keynote-024 ²⁷		
mPFS	8.9 (3.7–14.1)	NA	NA	7.7 (6.1-10.2)	11.5	10.9
mOS	15.8 (9.4–22.1)	NA	15.3 (13.4-17.5)	26.3 (18.3-40.4)	13.6	13.1
Surv. Rate (%)						
12 m	57	NA	54.5	NA	53.8	52.3
24 m	NA	NA	39.6	NA	29.6	35.9
36 m	NA	NA	31.6	43.7	16.7	28.2
PD-L1 ≥ 50; Pembrolizumab + PDCT				3 year update keynote-189 ²⁸		
mPFS	NA	8.8 (7.2-11.6)	NA	11.1 (9.1-14.4)	16.6	17.1
mOS	NA	20.6 (14.8-NR)	19.1 (15.5-22.1)	NR (20.4-NR)	18.9	19.3
Surv. Rate (%)						
6 m	NA	80.7 (70.1-87.9)	NA		80.5	78.4
12 m	NA	65.1 (53.3-74.5)	61.0	73.3	64.6	62.9
18 m	NA	54.6 (42.2-65.5)	NA	NA	51.7	52.1
24 m	NA	NA	42.7	51.9	41.1	44.1
PD-L1 1-49%; Pembrolizumab + PDCT						
mPFS	NA	5.9 (4.6-8.1)	NA	9.2 (7.8-13.1)	10.4	9.3
mOS	NA	16.3 (11.6-22.4)	11.8 (10.5-13.5)	21.8 (17.7-25.9)	12.3	11.5
Surv. Rate (%)						
6 m	NA	76.0 (64.6-84.1)	NA	NA	71.6	67.0
12 m	NA	59.6 (47.5-69.8)	49.1	71.7	50.6	48.9
18 m	NA	47.5 (35.6-58.6)	NA	NA	36.9	38.7
24 m	NA	NA	29.5	44.3	27.2	32.6

182 PDCT, platinum-based doublet chemotherapy; CT, pemetrexed; Surv. rate, overall survival rate; mPFS, median progression-free survival time;
183 mOS, median overall survival time; m, months; NA, not available; NR, not reached; US, United States of America; RCT, randomized control
184 trial.

185 ^a Contains patients with only good performance status i.e., ECOG PS 0 - 1;

186 ^b The Study contains different types of immunotherapies, for immunotherapy monotherapy, 95% of patients had pembrolizumab, and for

187 combination of immunotherapy with chemotherapy, 97% of patients had pembrolizumab plus PDCT/CT;

188 A.3 Figures

189

190

191 Figure A1. Comparison of modelled and observed bivariate association of baseline attributes
 192 and treatment for advanced (inoperable) NSCLC.

193 PS, Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group performance status; CCI, Charlson comorbidity
 194 index; BSC, best supportive care; Syst, systemic chemotherapy; Cisp. D, Cisplatin doublet
 195 chemotherapy; Carbo. D, Carboplatin doublet chemotherapy.

196 N.B., Statistical test results are reported in ESM Table 2 on column “% sim. pv <0.05”.

197 Large dots indicate the observed values (with 95% confidence interval from the template
 198 dataset).

199 Small dots indicate simulated values from 1000 runs of a non-personalized strategy, each run
 200 had 2196 simulated patients (sample size of template data).

201

202

203

204 Figure A2. Distribution of parameters of regression models used to simulate baseline
205 attributes and treatment decision of base-case model (a non-personalized strategy).

206 The model equations are given on top of each panel.
207 B_0 , intercept; error, random error with standard normal distribution; PS, Eastern Cooperative
208 Oncology Group performance status; CCI, Charlson comorbidity index; Year, year of
209 diagnosis; Age, age at diagnosis; BSC, best supportive care; Syst, systemic chemotherapy;
210 Cisp. D, Cisplatin doublet chemotherapy; Carbo. D, Carboplatin doublet chemotherapy;
211 Observed, parameter values obtained by fitting regression model on template dataset.

213 Figure A3. Comparison of modelled and observed time to event and proportion of events.
214 The modelled median, mean, restricted (rest.) mean and proportion in L2T and L3T were evaluated from 1000 runs of a non-personalized strategy.
215 Observed median, mean, and restricted mean were computed from the template dataset (Santeon registry 2008-2014).
216 L1T, L2T, L3T, and D, are first-line, second-line, third-line treatment, and death events, respectively.
217 PSF, progression-free survival; OS, overall survival; C.I, confidence interval; NA, not reached.
218 $i \rightarrow j$, from the i event to the j event. For i and $j =$ L1T, L2T, L3T, and D.
219 `` For panel c, restricted time was taken at the maximum percentile estimable ie., 50th percentile for T1L- \rightarrow T2L and 30th percentile for T2L- \rightarrow T3L.
220 All remaining events, the restricted time was taken at the 90th percentile.

221

222 Figure A4. Comparison of modelled and real-world progression-free survival (a) and overall
 223 survival (b) curves for patients with epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) mutations and
 224 treated with the first-line EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors (EGFR-TKIs).

225 EGFR-TKIs were gefitinib or erlotinib; C.I, confidence interval; RW, Real-world; 1L, start of
 226 first-line systemic treatment;

227 * The real-world data of 52 patients diagnosed and treated between 2008 and 2014 in Santeon
 228 hospitals ²⁹.

229 ** The reconstructed (digitized) real-world overall survival (OS) data of 147 patients treated between
 230 2015 and 2018 in Santeon hospitals. The OS data were digitized from the curve published by Cramer-
 231 van der Welle et al., 2021 ²⁴. Progression-free survival (PFS) data were not available.

232 *** Modelled data was simulated assuming EGFR-TKI benefit wear out after 15 months (t = 15m).

233 **** Modelled was simulated assuming a durable EGFR-TKIs benefit i.e., benefit last until disease
 234 progression or death (durable).

235 NB: The hazard ratios of EGFR-TKI were 0.43 and 0.36 for gefitinib and erlotinib compared to
 236 chemotherapy, respectively ⁵, and hazard ratio of 0.82 for prognostic value of EGFR positive
 237 compared to EGFR negative ¹².

238

239 Figure A5. Results of a deterministic sensitivity analysis on the impact of the long-term survivor
 240 fraction (cure rate) on progression-free survival (a) and overall survival (b) for patients with a
 241 high programmed death ligand 1 (PD-L1 \geq 50%) expression and treated with a first-line
 242 pembrolizumab monotherapy.

243 Cured, long-term survivor fraction.

244 * The reconstructed (digitized) progression-free and overall survival data of 83 patients diagnosed
 245 and treated between 2015 and 2018 in Santeon hospitals ²⁴.

246 ** Modelled data was simulated assuming different values of a long-term survivor fraction (cured)
 247 and a hazard ratio of 0.5 for pembrolizumab compared to chemotherapy ²⁰.

248 The black dot and interval bar (RCT 5-yr OS with 95% C.I) indicates a five-year overall survival
 249 with 95% confidence interval from Keynote-001 ³⁰.

- 251 1 Putter, H., Fiocco, M. & Geskus, R. B. Tutorial in biostatistics: competing risks and multi-state
252 models. *Stat Med* **26**, 2389-2430, doi:10.1002/sim.2712 (2007).
- 253 2 Beyersmann, J., Allignol, A. & Schumacher, M. *Competing Risks and Multistate Models with*
254 *R*. (Springer, 2012).
- 255 3 Williams, C., Lewsey, J. D., Briggs, A. H. & Mackay, D. F. Cost-effectiveness Analysis in R Using
256 a Multi-state Modeling Survival Analysis Framework: A Tutorial. *Med Decis Making* **37**, 340-
257 352, doi:10.1177/0272989X16651869 (2017).
- 258 4 Package 'flexsurv' (CRAN, 2019).
- 259 5 Holleman, M. S., van Tinteren, H., Groen, H. J., Al, M. J. & Uyl-de Groot, C. A. First-line
260 tyrosine kinase inhibitors in EGFR mutation-positive non-small-cell lung cancer: a network
261 meta-analysis. *Onco Targets Ther* **12**, 1413-1421, doi:10.2147/OTT.S189438 (2019).
- 262 6 Cramer-van der Welle, C. M. *et al.* Systematic evaluation of the efficacy-effectiveness gap of
263 systemic treatments in metastatic nonsmall cell lung cancer. *Eur Respir J* **52**,
264 doi:10.1183/13993003.01100-2018 (2018).
- 265 7 Kuijpers, C. *et al.* Association of molecular status and metastatic organs at diagnosis in
266 patients with stage IV non-squamous non-small cell lung cancer. *Lung Cancer* **121**, 76-81,
267 doi:10.1016/j.lungcan.2018.05.006 (2018).
- 268 8 Skoulidis, F. & Heymach, J. V. Co-occurring genomic alterations in non-small-cell lung cancer
269 biology and therapy. *Nat Rev Cancer* **19**, 495-509, doi:10.1038/s41568-019-0179-8 (2019).
- 270 9 Jordan, E. J. *et al.* Prospective Comprehensive Molecular Characterization of Lung
271 Adenocarcinomas for Efficient Patient Matching to Approved and Emerging Therapies.
272 *Cancer Discov* **7**, 596-609, doi:10.1158/2159-8290.CD-16-1337 (2017).
- 273 10 Forsythe, A. *et al.* A systematic review and meta-analysis of neurotrophic tyrosine receptor
274 kinase gene fusion frequencies in solid tumors. *Ther Adv Med Oncol* **12**, 1758835920975613,
275 doi:10.1177/1758835920975613 (2020).
- 276 11 Dietel, M. *et al.* Real-world prevalence of programmed death ligand 1 expression in locally
277 advanced or metastatic non-small-cell lung cancer: The global, multicenter EXPRESS study.
278 *Lung Cancer* **134**, 174-179, doi:10.1016/j.lungcan.2019.06.012 (2019).
- 279 12 Simons, M. *et al.* Observed versus modelled lifetime overall survival of targeted therapies
280 and immunotherapies for advanced non-small cell lung cancer patients - A systematic
281 review. *Crit Rev Oncol Hematol* **153**, 103035, doi:10.1016/j.critrevonc.2020.103035 (2020).
- 282 13 Peters, S. *et al.* Alectinib versus Crizotinib in Untreated ALK-Positive Non-Small-Cell Lung
283 Cancer. *N Engl J Med* **377**, 829-838, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1704795 (2017).
- 284 14 Solomon, B. J. *et al.* First-line crizotinib versus chemotherapy in ALK-positive lung cancer. *N*
285 *Engl J Med* **371**, 2167-2177, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1408440 (2014).
- 286 15 Wang, Z. L. *et al.* Anaplastic lymphoma kinase gene rearrangement predicts better prognosis
287 in NSCLC patients: A meta-analysis. *Lung Cancer* **112**, 1-9, doi:10.1016/j.lungcan.2017.07.029
288 (2017).
- 289 16 Shaw, A. T. *et al.* Crizotinib in ROS1-rearranged advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC):
290 updated results, including overall survival, from PROFILE 1001. *Ann Oncol* **30**, 1121-1126,
291 doi:10.1093/annonc/mdz131 (2019).
- 292 17 Long, G. V. *et al.* Dabrafenib and trametinib versus dabrafenib and placebo for Val600 BRAF-
293 mutant melanoma: a multicentre, double-blind, phase 3 randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*
294 **386**, 444-451, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(15)60898-4 (2015).
- 295 18 Kelly, R. J. Dabrafenib and trametinib for the treatment of non-small cell lung cancer. *Expert*
296 *Rev Anticancer Ther* **18**, 1063-1068, doi:10.1080/14737140.2018.1521272 (2018).
- 297 19 Hong, D. S. *et al.* Larotrectinib in patients with TRK fusion-positive solid tumours: a pooled
298 analysis of three phase 1/2 clinical trials. *Lancet Oncol* **21**, 531-540, doi:10.1016/S1470-
299 2045(19)30856-3 (2020).

300 20 Reck, M. *et al.* Pembrolizumab versus Chemotherapy for PD-L1-Positive Non-Small-Cell Lung
301 Cancer. *N Engl J Med* **375**, 1823-1833, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1606774 (2016).

302 21 Gandhi, L. *et al.* Pembrolizumab plus Chemotherapy in Metastatic Non-Small-Cell Lung
303 Cancer. *N Engl J Med* **378**, 2078-2092, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1801005 (2018).

304 22 Shaw, A. T. *et al.* Crizotinib versus chemotherapy in advanced ALK-positive lung cancer. *N*
305 *Engl J Med* **368**, 2385-2394, doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1214886 (2013).

306 23 Herbst, R. S. *et al.* Pembrolizumab versus docetaxel for previously treated, PD-L1-positive,
307 advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (KEYNOTE-010): a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*
308 **387**, 1540-1550, doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(15)01281-7 (2016).

309 24 Cramer-van der Welle, C. M. *et al.* Real-world outcomes versus clinical trial results of
310 immunotherapy in stage IV non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) in the Netherlands. *Sci Rep*
311 **11**, 6306, doi:10.1038/s41598-021-85696-3 (2021).

312 25 Velcheti, V., Hu, X. H., Piperdi, B. & Burke, T. Real-world outcomes of first-line
313 pembrolizumab plus pemetrexed-carboplatin for metastatic nonsquamous NSCLC at US
314 oncology practices. *Sci Rep-Uk* **11**, doi:ARTN 922210.1038/s41598-021-88453-8 (2021).

315 26 Waterhouse, D. *et al.* Real-world outcomes of immunotherapy-based regimens in first-line
316 advanced non-small cell lung cancer. *Lung Cancer* **156**, 41-49,
317 doi:10.1016/j.lungcan.2021.04.007 (2021).

318 27 Reck, M. *et al.* Five-Year Outcomes With Pembrolizumab Versus Chemotherapy for
319 Metastatic Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer With PD-L1 Tumor Proportion Score \geq 50. *J Clin*
320 *Oncol* **39**, 2339-2349, doi:10.1200/JCO.21.00174 (2021).

321 28 Gadgeel, S. *et al.* Updated Analysis From KEYNOTE-189: Pembrolizumab or Placebo Plus
322 Pemetrexed and Platinum for Previously Untreated Metastatic Nonsquamous Non-Small-Cell
323 Lung Cancer. *J Clin Oncol* **38**, 1505-1517, doi:10.1200/JCO.19.03136 (2020).

324 29 Sluga, R. *et al.* Utilization of Molecular Testing and Survival Outcomes of Treatment with
325 First- or Second-line Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors in Advanced Non-small Cell Lung Cancer in a
326 Dutch Population. *Anticancer Res* **38**, 393-400, doi:10.21873/anticancer.12235 (2018).

327 30 Garon, E. B. *et al.* Five-Year Overall Survival for Patients With Advanced NonSmall-Cell Lung
328 Cancer Treated With Pembrolizumab: Results From the Phase I KEYNOTE-001 Study. *J Clin*
329 *Oncol* **37**, 2518-2527, doi:10.1200/JCO.19.00934 (2019).

330